

A Monte Carlo Ray-Tracing Algorithm for Estimating View Factors for Thermal Analysis of Reactor Cores

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ABSTRACT

Monte Carlo Ray-Tracing (MCRT) is a widely used statistical method for simulating radiative heat transfer, especially in enclosures with participating media, *e.g.* gases or particles that absorb, emit, and scatter radiation. Central to MCRT is the concept of view factors, that describe the amount of radiation reaching one surface from another. First-order view factors specifically represent the direct exchange of radiation between surfaces without any intermediate reflections or scattering events.

In this paper, non-participating media are considered, and first-order view factors can sometimes be calculated for simple geometries using analytical formulas. For more complicated situations, MCRT addresses this geometrical complexity by statistically sampling the paths of bundles of rays. Each bundle is emitted from a surface and tracked as it moves through the enclosure. The fraction of bundles that reach another surface directly provides an estimate of the first-order view factor.

The ability of MCRT to manage complex geometrical configurations makes it well suited for applications involving high-temperature reactors (HTRs), where detailed representations of fuel and structural components are required. Moreover, the use of efficient ray-tracing implementations allows MCRT to be applied to computationally demanding problems such as design-basis accident transient analyses. In this work, MCRT is implemented through the Intel® Embree library for the TRUST platform. Two numerical verification cases are presented.

Keywords: Radiative heat transfer, MCRT, view factor, Intel® Embree.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear reactor design requires the integration of severe accidents in their conceptual stages to show their robustness for safety demonstration to safety authorities. One such design-basis accident for small reactors which are presently under development in many nuclear engineering start-ups over the world is the Loss Of Coolant Accident (LOCA).

During such an accident, the heat produced in the reactor core can no longer be evacuated using the liquid coolant as is usually the case and radiation becomes one of the main vectors of heat transfer. This mode of heat transfer is very complex due to the complex geometries arising within the accidental model itself, especially if core degradation is on-going. In this work, we limit ourselves to cases where heat transfer by radiation occurs through surfaces that are well defined, before any loss of core integrity.

In this situation, heat transfer by radiation is based on a model where the radiosity equations are solved for solid surfaces emitting through a transparent medium. This article describes the approach that is set up in the TRUST platform [1] for that effect.

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The following sections of this paper will first describe the theoretical background of the radiative heat transfer and view factors, followed by some implementation details of the computation of the view factors themselves in an in-house library. Finally, these view factors will be computed for an a simple geometry of pins, representative of reactor applications.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

This section will provide some insight on the context of radiation heat transfer and the specific context of transparent media bounded by opaque surfaces. Furthermore, it is assumed that the geometries are already meshed into simplices using an appropriate meshing tool.

2.1. From Radiosity to View Factors

Focusing on opaque, diffuse, grey surfaces in a transparent medium, the radiosity leaving a given patch of surface area A_i in these conditions is:

$$J_i(\mathbf{r}) = \varepsilon_i \sigma T_i^4(\mathbf{r}) + \rho_i G_i(\mathbf{r}) \quad (1)$$

where G_i is the irradiance received from all visible surfaces, *i.e.* the radiative flux incident per unit surface and ε_i (resp. ρ_i) the surface emissivity (resp. the reflectivity), T_i is the surface temperature and σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant.

The irradiance G_i can be expressed as

$$G_i(\mathbf{r}_i) = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{A_j} d^2r_j J_j(\mathbf{r}_j) \left[\frac{\cos \theta_{ij} \cos \theta_{ji}}{\|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j\|^2} \chi(\mathbf{r}_j, \mathbf{r}_i) \right] \quad (2)$$

where the geometrical notations are defined in Figure 1 and $\chi(\mathbf{r}_j, \mathbf{r}_i)$ is 0 if the segment between \mathbf{r}_j and \mathbf{r}_i crosses another surface of the geometrical setup, 1 otherwise [2].

Figure 1. Geometrical notations for Equation 2.

2.2. View Factors: A First-order Approximation

A first-order approximation for the radiosity is obtained by assuming that, in Equation 2, it is piecewise uniform, *i.e.* $\forall j \in \llbracket 1, n \rrbracket$, for surface A_j , $J_j(\mathbf{r}_j) = \bar{J}_j$.

Under these assumptions, Equation 1 is expressed as

$$J_i(\vec{r}_i) = \varepsilon_i \sigma \left(T_i^4(\vec{r}_i) \right) + \rho_i \sum_{j=1}^n \bar{J}_j f_{ij}(\vec{r}_i) \quad (3)$$

and integrating Equation 3 on \mathcal{A}_i leads to, $\forall i \in \llbracket 1, n \rrbracket$,

$$\bar{J}_i = \varepsilon_i \sigma \bar{T}_i^4 + \rho_i \sum_{j=1}^n F_{ij} \bar{J}_j \quad (4)$$

where coupling is entirely geometric, via the coefficients F_{ij} (configuration/view factors)—the foundation of both deterministic and Monte Carlo approaches [3]. These coefficients are written as:

$$F_{ij} = \frac{1}{A_i} \int_{\mathcal{A}_i} d^2 r_i f_{ij}(\vec{r}_i) \quad (5)$$

where A_i is the surface area \mathcal{A}_i and $f_{ij}(\vec{r}_i) d^2 r_i$, the differential view factor denoted as

$$f_{ij}(\vec{r}_i) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{\mathcal{A}_j} d^2 r_j \left[\frac{\cos \theta_{ij} \cos \theta_{ji}}{\|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j\|^2} \chi(\vec{r}_j, \vec{r}_i) \right] \quad (6)$$

The view factor represents the fraction of energy emitted from surface \mathcal{A}_i that lands on surface \mathcal{A}_j . Through these view factors, the heat transfer problem under the corresponding hypothesis is reduced to a purely geometric coupling problem.

From Equation 5 and Equation 6, the following relation may be deduced:

$$A_i F_{ij} = A_j F_{ji} \quad (7)$$

Apart from this reciprocity property, the other fundamental properties are closure, *i.e.* $\sum_j F_{ij} = 1$ for each emitter, and also, non-negativity of the view factors.

3. VIEW FACTORS WITH MONTE CARLO RAY-TRACING

3.1. Monte Carlo Ray-Tracing

In our case, Monte Carlo Ray-Tracing technique [4] is chosen to evaluate the first-order view factors. The main advantage is that this method can handle complex geometries while it can also be extended for second-order view factors [2]. By denoting $HS(\vec{r}_i, \vec{n}_i)$ as the hemisphere at position \vec{r}_i with an outward normal orientation of \vec{n}_i , Equation 6 can be re-written as:

$$f_{ij}(\vec{r}_i) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{HS(\vec{r}_i, \vec{n}_i)} d^2 \Omega_i \cos \theta_i \mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(\vec{r}_i, \vec{\Omega}_i) \quad (8)$$

where the characteristic function $\mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{A}_j}(\vec{r}_i, \vec{\Omega}_i)$ equals 1 if the first surface reached by a ray casted from \vec{r}_i and oriented as $\vec{\Omega}_i$ is \mathcal{A}_j , 0 otherwise.

For a Monte Carlo integration, the polar θ and azimuthal ϕ angles are estimated from uniformly distributed variables ξ_1^Ω and ξ_2^Ω as $\arccos \sqrt{1 - \xi_1^\Omega}$ and $2\pi \xi_2^\Omega$ respectively. Hence, the probability density function (*pdf*) for the angular variable $\vec{\Omega}$ is given as:

$$p(\vec{\Omega}) = \frac{\cos \theta}{\pi} \quad (9)$$

Furthermore, for the spatial sampling in the meshed geometry, the probability of picking on the simplicial cells is proportional to its surface area, *i.e.*

$$p(\mathcal{T}) = \frac{A_{\mathcal{T}}}{\sum_U A_U} \quad (10)$$

and the sampled point \vec{r} is obtained as

$$\vec{r} = (1 - \sqrt{\xi_1^S})\vec{v}_0 + \sqrt{\xi_1^S}(1 - \xi_2^S)\vec{v}_1 + \sqrt{\xi_1^S}\xi_2^S\vec{v}_2 \quad (11)$$

with \vec{v}_i as the vertices of the sampled triangle in the mesh. Thus, the global estimator for the view factor is given as:

$$\hat{F}_{ij} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{1}_{A_j}(\vec{r}_i^{(k)}, \vec{\Omega}^{(k)}), \quad pdf(\vec{r}_i^{(k)}) \sim \mathcal{U}(A_i), \quad pdf(\vec{\Omega}^{(k)}) \sim \cos \theta / \pi. \quad (12)$$

Algorithm 1 outlines the key elements to compute view factors between surfaces for radiation heat transfer using MCRT. Using an importance sampling technique for the angular distribution, leading to Lambertian-distributed directions, rays are created from the considered emitter surface. In our case, rays that intersect with the emitter surface itself are neglected. Finally, the rays that hit the considered receiver surface are tallied.

The view factor from surface i to surface j is approximated as the ratio given by:

$$F_{ij} \approx \frac{H_j}{N} \quad (13)$$

where H_j is the number of rays hitting surface j , and N is the total number of rays emitted.

Algorithm 1 Monte Carlo View Factor Calculation

- 1: **Input:** Emitter surface, scene geometry, number of rays N
 - 2: **Output:** View factors F_{ij} (fraction of rays from emitter i hitting receiver j)
 - 3: **for** each ray k from 1 to N **do**
 - 4: Sample a point and direction on emitter surface i using Lambertian distribution
 - 5: Avoid self-hit: Ensure ray does not intersect emitter i immediately after emission
 - 6: Trace ray through the scene
 - 7: **if** ray intersects receiver surface j **then**
 - 8: Increment hit count for surface j : $H_j \leftarrow H_j + 1$
 - 9: **end if**
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: Compute view factor $F_{ij} = \frac{H_j}{N}$ for each receiver surface j
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3.2. MCRT with Intel® Embree

Intel® Embree [5, 6] is a collection of high-performance ray-tracing kernels, meticulously optimized for contemporary multi-core and many-core CPUs, particularly those featuring Intel vectorised instruction sets such as SSE, AVX, AVX2, and AVX-512.

The library is designed to accelerate the computationally intensive tasks of ray-scene intersection and traversal, which are fundamental to both real-time and offline rendering pipelines. Embree employs a range of acceleration structures, including bounding volume hierarchies (BVHs) and spatial splits, to

minimize ray traversal times and maximize cache efficiency. Its architecture is highly modular, allowing developers to select and customize components such as ray packets, single-ray traversal, and various geometric primitives (e.g., triangles, quads, curves, and instanced scenes). The library's API is written in C++, providing low-level control over memory management, threading, and SIMD vectorisation, which is crucial for achieving optimal performance on modern hardware.

The Intel® Embree API provides a comprehensive set of functions for ray-tracing, scene management, and acceleration structure construction. This is an overview of the core function categories and some key functions typically used in the API. A typical Workflow is set up as follows:

- Initialize a device (`rtcNewDevice`) and scene (`rtcNewScene`).
- Create and configure geometries, setting vertex/index buffers and attributes (`rtcNewGeometry`, `rtcSetSharedGeometryBuffer`, ...).
- Attach geometries (`rtcAttachGeometry`) to the scene.
- Commit the scene to build acceleration structures (`rtcCommitScene`).
- Trace rays using `rtcIntersect` functions. `rtcInitIntersectContext` initializes an intersection context for ray queries. `rtcIntersect4/8/16` are packed ray intersection functions for tracing 4, 8, or 16 rays simultaneously through vectorised patterns.
- Release resources when done (`rtcReleaseGeometry`, `rtcReleaseScene`).

This work is implemented in the form of an experimental library `embree2TRUST` that loads a mesh from a MED format file for TRUST and builds the corresponding Embree geometry and scene from it. From there on, the MCRT algorithm described as in Algorithm 1 is called for all emitter surfaces. For the sake of brevity, the obtained set of view factors is post-processed through an optimisation algorithm to enforce reciprocity, closure, and positivity.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, numerical results on two cases are presented. The first one is an analytical case where the view factors are computed on the faces of a nested cube within a cube, while the second one is a more realistic test case with pin cells as those encountered in light water reactor systems.

4.1. Academic case for analytical verification

This simple case is illustrated in Figure 2a. In this case, the faces of both cubes emit on all the other faces. This situation corresponds to computing the view factors in rectangular emitter described by the cases in [7]. There is no "self-hitting", *i.e.* face L1 does not emit on itself such that its view factor is zero. Furthermore, some faces do not "see" each other, *e.g.* L2 and S1. The nested cubes geometry is meshed into triangles using the GMSH mesher [8]. This case is meant as a verification for our implementation to ensure that the MCRT algorithm is working as expected.

Table I shows the results for faces S1 and L1 from the small and large cubes respectively (*cf.* Figure 2a; with good agreement between the computed and analytical values. The same is observed for the other pair of faces which are not detailed here for conciseness. Furthermore, Figure 2b shows the mean and maximum variance for the view factor matrix entries with the number of rays sampled for the MCRT algorithm. It can be observed that the expected $1/N$ behaviour is obeyed for both, except as the variance goes below $1e-7$. This is probably due to the fact that Embree uses single-precision floating-point (fp32) for storing ray hit and intersection data.

4.2. Fuel Pin Case

In this case, a 2D row of pin cells emitting into the fluid (in green in Figure 3) is considered. Figure 4 illustrates the view factors matrix, the variance with the number of samples and its distribution. The matrix is symmetric and the values of the variance are within satisfactory margins.

(a) 3D Geometry of Concentric Cubes

(b) Variance Plot

Figure 2. Concentric Cubes Case and Variance Analysis

Table I. Results for the view factors for face S1 of the small cube and face L1 of the large cube, to and from each other. The results are compared to the analytical values computed from Howell [7].

	Analytical [7]	Monte Carlo	N. of Samples
$F_{L1 \rightarrow S1}$	0.1986	0.1986	5×10^6
$F_{S1 \rightarrow L1}$	0.7945	0.7945	5×10^6

In addition, Figure 5 provides the results concerning the statistical convergence of the relative error on the view factors as the number of samples is varied. While the mean error converges very quickly, more samples are required for the maximum error for which the convergence occurs with a slower rate. In the same figure, on the right, the inter-run variances are plotted, *i.e.* the variability of the results for different independent simulations with fixed number of samples per simulation; five runs here in this study. These independent runs are important to estimate the mean value of the required physical quantity such as the view factors and the associated variance.

Figure 3. Meshed geometry of the pin cells.

Figure 6a gives the time for the MCRT algorithm with the Embree implementation with various sample sizes. The results are plotted by normalising to the time for the 5000 case. Figure 6b provides the strong scaling plots up to 16 cores on a Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-10875H CPU @ 2.30GHz workstation. The behaviour remains mostly linear in the logscale setting.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, a procedure based on the MCRT algorithm to compute view factors for the TRUST code is implemented: the user provides a meshed geometry file which is used to create the scene for the Embree library.

Figure 4. View factor matrix and the distribution of the variances.

Figure 5. Convergence indicators with respect to the number of samples.

(a) Computational times wrt. number of samples.

(b) Computational times wrt. number of cores.

Figure 6. Computational trends.

This work has set the first software bricks to provide users with the ability to compute view factors to be used within a simple radiative heat transfer within transparent media. Further work is required to improve the present implementation and optimise the computational times for the MCRT. One interesting avenue for such work is to port this algorithm to GPU.

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